

Cognitive Management and Orchestration of Resources in the Edge Cloud Continuum

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Executive Summary

Modern organizations increasingly deploy applications across the so-called Edge-Cloud continuum. Such deployment requires a high degree of human intervention. Furthermore, the management of applications during runtime also requires heavy configuration. To automate this process, there are today several tools that manage (orchestrate) the deployment and running of applications. Still, with the increasing trend to bring applications, services, and processes closer to data sources (far Edge), there is a growing need to have an efficient and flexible orchestration of resources from the far Edge to Cloud.

This white paper provides an overview and a comparative analysis of cognitive and intelligent resource management techniques for the Edge-Cloud continuum, which are developed in six European research and innovation projects: CODECO, COGNIFOG, COGNIT, MLSysOps, ENACT, and DECICE. These projects address the growing complexity of managing distributed computing resources across Cloud and Edge environments. In this direction they develop advanced AI-driven approaches to optimizing performance, scalability, and security.

The document emphasizes the role of cognitive techniques, such as Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), in automating resource allocation, workload distribution, and system adaptation in real-time. These technologies are essential for managing heterogeneous environments that span from IoT devices at the Edge to centralized Cloud data centres.

Key challenges in this domain include ensuring reliable network connectivity, protecting data privacy, managing heterogeneous resources, and scaling deployments efficiently. Each of the projects discussed in this paper offers a unique approach and solution to these challenges. Specifically:

- CODECO introduces a cross-layer orchestration framework that integrates data-compute-network perspectives to ensure seamless management of containerized applications across the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum.
- COGNIFOG focuses on self-aware AI-based orchestration for real-time decision-making in dynamic environments.
- COGNIT provides a serverless approach to Edge-Cloud management with a focus on sovereignty and flexibility.
- MLSysOps enables autonomous and adaptive end-to-end system management for Edge-Cloud environments.
- ENACT specializes in the optimized allocation of HPC workloads with a focus on scalability and efficiency.
- DECICE emphasizes the development and use of decentralized decision-making and privacy-preserving AI techniques for real-time orchestration across Edge-Cloud infrastructures.

The white paper concludes by comparing these approaches, highlighting their commonalities (e.g., the use of AI for cognitive resource management) and their differences in terms of orchestration strategies (centralized vs. decentralized) and application domains. Best practices derived from these projects are also discussed towards providing valuable insights for practical solutions and future developments in Edge-Cloud resource management.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTO	Application-Level Traffic Optimization
API	Application Programming Interface
APM	Application Programming Model
ARM	Advanced RISC Machine
CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT or IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum
CPUs	Central Processing Unit
CV	Computer Vision
DevOps	Development and Operations
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FaaS	Function as a Service
GNN	Graph Neural Networks
GPU	Graph Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
MDM	Metadata Manager
MDS	Media Delivery System
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation component
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning
QoE	Quality of Experience
RSUs	Roadside Units
SaaS	Software as a Service
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TMA	Telematic Medical Applications
VAM	VRU Awareness Module
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
ZTP	Zero-Touch Provisioning

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1 Introduction to Cloud Edge Continuum Management

1.1 Scope and purpose

Modern organizations are deploying IT applications and workloads across Edge-Cloud computing infrastructures. These applications are distributed across the Edge-Cloud continuum. For instance, data intensive parts of an application are usually executed within the Cloud, while real time functions tend to be deployed and operated at the Edge.

In this context, Edge-Cloud infrastructure deployers and operators strive to achieve optimal resource utilization, while maintaining security, data privacy, and credibility in their operations. This is also the reason cognitive and intelligent resource management in the Edge-Cloud continuum is becoming increasingly important towards optimizing the processing of data across diverse computing environments. In this direction, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) techniques into Edge-Cloud management layers allows for the automatic adaptation of resources at different OSI Layers. This enables data to be processed optimally, whether closer to the user at the Edge, or when residing in centralized Cloud environments. AI-driven Cloud optimization enhances resource allocation and system performance by dynamically distributing resources to address the requirements of changing workloads. For instance, techniques such as Machine Learning (ML) and predictive analytics are employed to automate resource provisioning, scaling, and workload planning, towards improving efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Furthermore, the seamless integration of diverse computing and data environments from core Cloud to Edge is essential for achieving a trustworthy AI-enabled computing continuum. This integration addresses the growing complexity of requirements and the exponential increase in IoT data across various sectors and contexts.

The present white paper presents different approaches to managing and orchestrating resources across the Edge-Cloud computing continuum, notably approaches that have been devised, implemented, and validated in different EU funded projects. Emphasis is paid on cognitive and intelligent techniques that balance trade-offs in complex scenarios, including data driven techniques that leverage machine learning and other forms of AI to orchestrate and manage resources (e.g., containers) within Edge Cloud environments.

1.2 State of the Art and Challenges

Cognitive and intelligent resource management in the Edge-Cloud continuum is evolving rapidly, driven by the need to efficiently manage resources across diverse computing environments. Cross-layer resource management techniques play a prominent role in this context, as they enable seamless integration and optimization of resources from IoT devices to Cloud data centres. Such techniques involve coordinating resources across different layers of the network stack to ensure that computing tasks are distributed optimally between Edge and Cloud environments. Such approaches enhance performance, improve energy efficiency, and reduce latency, given that they process data closer to where it is generated.

Function as a Service (FaaS) is another emerging paradigm within this continuum, which offers a serverless architecture and provide resource management techniques around it. For instance, FaaS allows developers to run code without managing the underlying infrastructure. FaaS is very well-suited for Edge computing scenarios due to its ability to handle isolated, stateless functions that can be executed in response to specific events. This makes FaaS an ideal solution for applications requiring high scalability and low-latency processing, such as

IoT and real-time data analytics. The integration of FaaS with Edge computing enables developers to leverage the benefits of both paradigms, which allows them to optimize resource usage while maintaining flexibility and cost-effectiveness¹.

AI-based resource management further enhances this ecosystem by introducing intelligent decision-making capabilities². AI technologies such as machine learning and deep learning are employed to predict workloads, optimize resource allocation, and automate scaling processes. Such AI-driven approaches ensure that resources are used efficiently, based on dynamic adaptation to changing demands and minimization of the operational costs. Based on AI technologies, Cloud platforms can offer more robust services, improving system performance and reliability across the entire compute continuum.

Nevertheless, the cognitive and intelligent management of resources in the Edge-Cloud continuum presents several considerable challenges, which stem from the need to efficiently handle distributed, heterogeneous, and dynamic resources across Cloud, fog, and Edge computing environments. Some of the main challenges include:

- **Providing Network Connectivity and Reliability:** reliable network connectivity is a major challenge due to intermittent connections, latency issues, and bandwidth limitations.
- **Infrastructure Requirements:** Robust network infrastructure is necessary to support seamless data flow between Edge devices and Cloud servers.
- **Increased Attack Surface:** The distributed nature of Edge computing increases the potential for security breaches, as the Cloud attack surface is enhanced based on the potential vulnerabilities of Edge devices.
- **Data Protection:** Protecting sensitive data at the Edge requires robust encryption, authentication protocols, and secure communication channels.
- **Heterogeneous Resource Management and Optimization:** Managing resources across heterogeneous devices with varying capabilities is complex as multiple techniques must be combined, and trade-offs must be resolved.
- **Scalability:** Scaling deployments to meet growing workloads while managing limited processing power and energy resources is also challenging.
- **Orchestration Complexity:** Deploying and managing applications across the continuum requires sophisticated orchestration to efficiently handle the lifecycle of applications and data sources. In several cases, automation tools are needed to streamline device provisioning, software updates, and remote management.
- **Data Portability:** This is also a need to ensure seamless data transfer between Edge and Cloud environments while maintaining data integrity.
- **Adaptation to Dynamic Environments:** There is also a need to dynamically adapt to unpredictable workloads, while optimizing the placement and migration of different services. This is typically challenging as it requires predicting, detecting, and reacting to workload fluctuations in ways that maintain performance across the continuum. Likewise, deciding where to place services (Cloud vs. Edge) based on current conditions is a complex decision-making process that requires advanced AI-driven solution.
- **Energy efficiency.** Energy efficiency is a critical concern due to the increasing number of connected devices, the scale of data processing, and the need for sustainable operations. Addressing energy efficiency requires a balanced approach across both Edge and Cloud components, considering factors like hardware, software, network, and system-level optimizations.

¹ Alessio Matricardi, Alessandro Bocci, Stefano Forti, and Antonio Brogi. 2023. Simulating FaaS Orchestration in The Cloud-Edge Continuum. In Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Flexible Resource and Application Management on the Edge (FRAME '23). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3589010.3594893>.

² J, Anurag. (2024). Review of AI-driven Cloud Optimization. International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management. 08. 1-5. 10.55041/IJSREM34000

A wide range of EU funded projects carry out research to address one or more of the above-listed challenges. As illustrated in following sections they employ advanced AI techniques for resource optimization, enhanced security measures, and intelligent orchestration frameworks that can adapt to changing conditions in real-time.

1.3 Technology and Market Trends

In recent years there is a growing demand for Edge computing services, because of the shift of the data from Cloud to the Edge. Likewise, there is also a rising demand for Edge-Cloud container orchestration and resource management services, which is reflected on market demand for relevant products and tools. As a prominent example, the FaaS market is experiencing rapid growth, driven by the increasing adoption of serverless computing across various industries and by the shift from traditional DevOps to serverless architectures. FaaS offers significant advantages, including reduced operational overhead and cost efficiency through a pay-as-you-go pricing model. The FaaS market is projected to grow significantly, with estimates suggesting it will reach USD 17.70 billion by 2024 and USD 44.71 billion by 2029 i.e. at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 20.36%³. FaaS is increasingly integrated with Edge computing environments to provide more efficient resource management, while reducing latency and improving performance.

As another example, the Kubernetes market is characterized by several key trends that reflect its growing importance⁴. One of the most significant trends is the rapid growth of the Kubernetes solutions market, which is projected to expand from USD 1.46 billion in 2019 to USD 9.69 billion by 2031 i.e., based on a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 23.4% during the specified period. This growth is driven by Kubernetes' ability to automate the deployment, management, and scaling of containerized applications. Another trend is the increasing adoption of Kubernetes across organizations worldwide. Over 60% of enterprises have adopted Kubernetes, with adoption rates reaching as high as 96% according to some surveys⁵. This widespread adoption is due in part to Kubernetes' cost efficiencies, scalability, and ability to support multi-Cloud environments.

Moreover, there is a growing emphasis on using AI tools to optimize Kubernetes operations. The integration of AI into Kubernetes management is seen as a major trend in Edge-Cloud computing applications, where AI workloads are increasingly being deployed.

1.4 Structure of the Paper

The paper includes a dedicated chapter for the presentation of the approach of each project. Specifically, following this introductory paragraph, the remainder of the whitepaper is structured as follows:

- Section 2 is devoted to the description of the Edge-Cloud resource management and orchestration approach of the CODECO project.
- Section 3 is devoted to the description of the Edge-Cloud resource management and orchestration approach of the COGNIFOG project.
- Section 4 is devoted to the description of the Edge-Cloud resource management and orchestration approach of the COGNIT project.
- Section 5 is devoted to the description of the Edge-Cloud resource management and orchestration approach of the MYSYSOPS project.
- Section 6 is devoted to the description of the Edge-Cloud resource management and orchestration approach of the ENACT project.

³ <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/function-as-a-service-market>

⁴ <https://www.skyquestt.com/report/kubernetes-market>

⁵ <https://www.redhat.com/en/resources/kubernetes-adoption-security-market-trends-overview>

- Section 7 is devoted to the description of the Edge-Cloud resource management and orchestration approach of the DECICE project.
- Section 8 provides a critical comparison of the approaches of the different projects. It highlights commonalities and differences of the various approaches, while consolidated best practices stemming from the work and experiences of all projects.

2 CODECO: Cognitive, Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration

2.1 Overview

CODECO is a Kubernetes-oriented orchestration framework that aims at bringing more flexibility into the orchestration of applications and their micro-services across the far Edge to Cloud. The challenges driving the vision of CODECO relate with the need to support massive IoT deployments in 6G, i.e., being able to handle applications and their components with high portability across heterogeneous networks. A second challenge relates with being able to ensure an adequate support to the data workflow, while ensuring that applications meet the desired Quality of Service (QoS) requirements.

To achieve this support, CODECO considers the Edge-Cloud infrastructure from different perspectives (computation, network, data) which need to be orchestrated as a single entity:

- The **networking perspective**, where the network is perceived both as the underlay and overlay infrastructure required to support the deployment of containerised applications across Edge-Cloud.
- The **data observability perspective**, bringing input on the data dependencies that micro-services may have, and that is important to consider during the application deployment and re-deployment; and
- The **computational perspective**, bringing input on the suitable nodes to serve an application, taking into consideration.

CODECO addresses the orchestration across these three different perspectives in an integrated approach, which is named as **data-compute-network orchestration**, represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The CODECO data-compute-network approach for CEI.

2.2 Unique Value Proposition

The **unique value proposition** of the CODECO project lies in its ability to jointly orchestrate computational, network and data observability resources across Edge-Cloud, to best serve the QoS requirements of applications. These requirements are provided by the user during deployment.

CODECO deploys applications considering target performance profiles that the user defines during deployment. Two of these target performance profiles are **greenness** and **resilience**.

AI/ML is used to provide recommendations to the CODECO novel graph-based scheduler, who then deploys the application and its micro-services. Furthermore, AI/ML is used to understand the overall deployment stability, via feedback provided by the scheduler on the assignments and the relevancy of provided recommendations.

By combining **AI-driven resource management**, **dynamic task offloading**, **advanced network communication**, and **sustainable energy practices**, CODECO aims to unlock the full potential of the Edge-Cloud continuum, enhancing both operational efficiency and the overall user experience across diverse applications.

2.3 Technical Architecture

Relevant in CODECO is an adaptation based on application requirements and user requirements. A functional representation of CODECO and its open-source components is provided in **Figure 2**. Based on this functional level, CODECO offers the following aspects:

- **Automated configuration**, focusing on supporting application setup and application runtime across Edge-Cloud, by taking into consideration compute, network, and data aspects. The key aspects of this contribution are supported by the CODECO *Advanced Configuration and Management (ACM)* component.
- **Data as a resource**. CODECO addresses, via its *Metadata Manager (MDM)* component data as a resource in the sense that available snapshots from the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure, integrating different perspectives (application, user, system, data, network) at different instants of the CODECO operational workflow can be provided to different CODECO components, to assist in detecting relevant changes.
- **Dynamic scheduling and workload migration**. Supported by the CODECO component *Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM)*, CODECO brings in novel QoS models that consider data-network-compute requirements to provide a best match between applications and available infrastructure (nodes, their computational and data properties, as well as network nodes and links), and to schedule and re-schedule application workloads across single cluster and federated cluster environments, considering application and user requirements.
- **Context-awareness and privacy preserving decentralised learning**. CODECO relies on context-awareness to be able to achieve a joint data-network-compute orchestration, and on privacy-preserving decentralised learning and inference to best support readjustment of aspects such as the processing capability, computational resources, networking resources and interconnections in real-time. Context-awareness and decentralised learning are part of the CODECO *Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning (PDLC)* component.
- **Infrastructure adaptation based on a cross-layer data-compute-network approach**. Via the CODECO *Network Management and Adaptation component (NetMA)*, CODECO assists in adapting not just computational (node resources) but also the networking infrastructure interconnecting such nodes, having as starting point for the exposure of metadata within 1 cluster and across federated clusters, from far Edge to Cloud.

Figure 2: Functional representation of the CODECO Kubernetes framework and its components.

The only interface of CODECO to the user, as shown in **Figure 2**, is the ACM component, which focuses on supporting application setup and runtime from the far Edge to the Cloud, considering the input provided by the user.

The user in CODECO is perceived as an **application developer (DEV)** or as a **cluster manager (MGT)**.

To setup CODECO, a user relies on the CODECO framework. ACM installs the entire CODECO framework, handling the overall CODECO configuration. The user can specify, via the CODECO **Application Model (CAM)**, the requirements of the application and of its micro-services. These requirements are relevant to allow CODECO to deploy the application across CEI in an efficient way.

Via CAM, the user specifies also **target performance profiles** that is used in CODECO (PDLC) to meet a specific level of **greenness**, or **resilience** during its operation.

Once CODECO is installed, all CODECO components can be used. The CODECO components have been devised to allow each component to work independently, with other future open orchestration frameworks, requiring little adaptation.

The **CODECO MDM** component provides data and system observability to the other CODECO components, treating data as an integral part of the application workload, and integrating observability perspectives from different categories, e.g., application perspective, system perspective, network perspective, at different points in the CODECO operational workflow.

SWM handles the scheduling and rescheduling of the application workload, based on the *CODECO Application Model (CAM)*. CAM is supported by ACM and provided by the user during application setup, based on the novel data-compute-network approach proposed by CODECO.

The currently available approach in SWM for handling placement decisions relies on a graph-based optimization approach which in contrast to the Kubernetes filtering and score approach is expected to provide an optimal match between application requirements and available resources (computational, network, data). SWM is also a control plane component, co-located with ACM and the Kubernetes control plane, in master nodes.

PDLC is at the heart of the CODECO orchestration. Based on the infrastructure data collected by ACM (via Prometheus), NetMA, and MDM, PDLC has two functions. Firstly, it provides an aggregated cost view of a specific target performance profile for the available infrastructure which can be used by other components and is currently being considered in SWM to further define the optimal workload placement. Secondly, it provides an estimate on the overall system stability based on privacy-preserving decentralised learning approaches. PDLC is currently envisaged to operate on both Kubernetes master and worker nodes.

NetMA provides the network awareness to CODECO and handles also secure connectivity across pods. Network awareness is provided via network probing based on the sub-component Network State Management (NSM). Then, exposure of network metrics (across multi-cluster environments) is based on the ALTO protocol. NetMA provides in addition **secure connectivity** via **L2S-M**⁶. Hence, NetMA is a component responsible for interconnecting the *Software-defined Networking (SDN)* world with Kubernetes.

To be able to achieve a flexible orchestration, CODECO counts with monitoring across the three different CEI infrastructure perspectives. NetMA monitors the networking infrastructure; MDM monitors the data infrastructure; ACM monitors the system (computational nodes) infrastructure based on the Kubernetes metrics server Prometheus^{7,8}. This approach allows to explore the integration of new metrics as well as of providing the collected metrics of CODECO to future orchestration frameworks.

The CODECO framework is deployed as an application: each CODECO component is based on a modular approach, integrating different sub-components that are expected to be built as one or more independent (dockerized) micro-services.

The overall CODECO architecture is illustrated in Figure 3 considering as starting point the CODECO operation within a single cluster deployment and addressing design considerations to be taken into consideration during the second part of the project.

Figure 3: The CODECO reference architecture, single cluster operation.

6 <http://l2sm.io>

7 <https://prometheus.io/>

8 The current version of CODECO considers Prometheus as basis for the metrics gathering and analysis. However, for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments the consortium is also considering Thanos due to the higher availability, and extended storage capabilities.

2.4 Validating Use Cases

2.4.1 P1: Smart Monitoring of Public Infrastructure | Smart Cities

The objective of this use case⁹ is to enhance traffic flow and pedestrian safety in Göttingen while bolstering the Smart City initiative through a road monitoring and analytics system at the far Edge. This system includes two components: traffic monitoring at the city's outskirts and pedestrian distribution monitoring in the city center. It gathers and analyses data on traffic and pedestrian behavior at the Edge to optimize management, reduce congestion, and improve pedestrian safety and comfort, providing valuable insights for city planning.

Figure 4: CODECO P1 system architecture.

The city's periphery is equipped with thermal cameras, computing units, and communication units for real-time traffic data collection and analysis, tracking vehicle counts and congestion levels. These insights aim to optimize traffic flow, reduce bottlenecks, and enhance traffic efficiency. In the city center, LiDARs, computing units, communication units, and data analytics track pedestrian movement patterns and density, improving safety, managing crowd flow, and informing city planning. The back-end data center processes real-time results at the Edge and visualizes them for the public. As the pilot progresses, data will be evaluated to adjust traffic patterns, modify transport routes, and potentially redesign city layouts for better pedestrian and vehicular flow.

The system architecture represented in Figure 4 considering one cluster deployment, details both non-CODECO and CODECO components. The Kubernetes control plane with CODECO nodes runs in the Cloud but can also be deployed at the near Edge. Worker nodes are deployed in Edge nodes co-located with cameras across the city. CODECO components are placed in both the Cloud (Kubernetes master node) and Edges (Kubernetes worker nodes). Each implementation location is equipped with an Edge device featuring sensors like thermal cameras or LiDAR systems. An Edge node is equivalent to a Kubernetes worker node, ensuring autonomous computational and data processing capabilities while remaining interconnected within the network. Cloud dataset, including video and point Cloud data, is pre-processed and stored locally for future reference, audits, and to manage data sensitivity.

⁹ Video demonstrating CODECO Use Case 1: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pm2D_dt3coA&t=6s

2.4.2 P2: Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility | Mobility

Figure 5: CODECO P3 use-case system representation.

This use case leverages CODECO to enhance the safety of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) in urban environments through a Vehicular Digital Twin¹⁰. It utilizes Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) Roadside Units (RSUs) and cameras to collect essential data for tracking vehicles and pedestrians, which is then fed into the Digital Twin to identify and alert on dangerous situations or behaviours. The deployment faces infrastructure challenges, requiring information processing near V2X nodes to maintain low latency and ensure real-time tracking.

The primary pilot scenario is set in the mobility environment of the Universidad Politecnica de Cataluna campus "Campus Nord" in Barcelona, featuring a mix of pedestrian zones, bike lanes, and car lanes. This setting provides an ideal testing ground due to its size and diversity, allowing for the evaluation of various transportation modes and control measures.

2.4.3 P3: Media Delivery System across Decentralized Edge-Cloud | Smart Cities

This use case emphasizes the smart and efficient distribution of media content, including video streaming, gaming, and AR/XR content, across a multi-domain, multi-cluster Edge-Cloud infrastructure¹¹. It optimizes both connectivity from the underlying transport network and computational resources supporting MDS streamers and distribution logic.

The operation of P3 within a single cluster is depicted in **Error! Reference source not found..** Initially, end-users request a service from the MDS (step 1), prompting the MDS to interact

¹⁰ Video demonstrating CODECO Use Case 2: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8wbkzT_aPdI

¹¹ Video Demonstrating CODECO Use Case 3: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sazvWuCOpw8&t=136s>

Figure 6: Operation of the CODECO Media Delivery System (single cluster scenario).

with CODECO components to gather network metrics for various delivery points (step 2). After obtaining this data, the MDS evaluates the combined compute and network information, including content availability, to determine the most suitable delivery point for the end-users (step 3). Consequently, end-users access the chosen delivery point.

In contrast, the multi-cluster scenario represented involves optimizing delivery points across the Edge-Cloud continuum due to end-user presence in different areas. The MDS identifies a potential end-user base that could enhance the delivery system (step 1). To determine the optimal node for deploying a new delivery endpoint, the MDS interacts with CODECO components to identify potential sites, collecting both network and compute metrics (step 2). After processing this information, the MDS decides on the best location for the new delivery point, ensuring optimization. The new endpoint is then interconnected with the Origin MDS node and the rest of the MDS network via L2S-M overlay for content distribution (step 3). Once operational, the new endpoint serves end-user requests as outlined in the single-cluster scenario.

2.4.4 P4: Demand-side Management in Decentralized Grids | Energy

This use case focuses on implementing an active demand response decentralized management system for building decarbonization¹². It aims to optimize energy usage, improve sustainability, and enhance the resilience of buildings by integrating renewable energy sources and enabling intelligent demand response actions. The use case also emphasizes the joint orchestration of computational and networking resources to ensure efficient coordination and management of energy-consuming

Figure 7: CODECO, P4 System for Demand-side Management in Decentralized Grids.

¹² Video Demonstrating CODECO Use Case 4: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WeV0PC5eccQ>

devices and the networking infrastructure within buildings. It focuses on achieving a holistic view of data in the CEI continuum, enabling comprehensive monitoring, analysis, and replication of energy-related data.

In the scope of the use case, CODECO leverages the power of Kubernetes to build a decentralized energy management system. Based on the integration of worker nodes (i.e., Edge devices) and the use of CODECO tools (e.g., ACM, PDLC), this use case demonstrates efficient resource utilization, scalability, resilience, and adaptability in energy management operations.

An early architecture for the use case is presented in Figure 7. The architecture consists of the following components:

- **Edge Devices:** These are devices located at various energy generation and consumption points, equipped with sensors, and connected to the local energy infrastructure. Examples include smart meters, renewable energy sources (e.g., solar panels, wind turbines), and energy storage systems. Each Edge device acts as a worker node within the K8s system, capable of performing computations and data processing independently.
- **Master Node:** The master node serves as the central control plane within the Kubernetes system. It manages and orchestrates the distributed resources and tasks across the Edge devices. The master node is responsible for coordinating energy generation, consumption, and optimization algorithms, as well as collecting and analysing data from the Edge devices.
- **Energy UC Cluster:** The Energy UC cluster consists of the master node and multiple worker nodes (Edge devices). It provides a scalable and resilient infrastructure for managing the de-centralized energy system. The Kubernetes cluster handles workload scheduling, resource allocation, and load balancing to optimize energy management tasks.

2.4.5 P5: Wireless AGV Control via CODECO for Flexible Factories | Manufacturing

The use-case explores AGVs (Automated Guided Vehicles) handling goods within a warehouse, while being subject to remote control and requiring real-time support¹³. It aims at providing a more flexible control to support fleets with a larger number of AGVs, and to support an increasing number of tasks/goods to be transported. Based on a higher level of autonomy, it is possible to increase overall efficiency while reducing operational costs. The integration of wireless technologies to support the control of AGVs, e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi 6/7, is therefore explored in the scope of CODECO. However, wireless connectivity also implies that the control of AGV systems is prone to interference and intermittent connectivity, which requires CODECO to provide a higher degree of adaptation. Hence, in addition to the wireless connectivity aspects concerning interference mitigation, synchronization, this use-case demonstrates the CODECO capability to proactively adapt the overall network energy consumption and to mitigate interference and failures. The use-case is developed in phases starting from a single cluster and a static control plane to the deployment and use of federated clusters.

The proposed solution in this use-case consists of CODECO and of a set of AGV fleet Apps to assist the deployment of the use-case, and to play with CODECO components, as represented in Figure 8. The key innovation aspects relate to the use of context-awareness and behaviour estimation to provide a higher degree of flexibility to the overall system, thus

¹³ Video Demonstrating CODECO Use Case 5: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZDpM-VLvDgk>

allowing control of AGVs to be handled in a decentralized way. This is expected to bring benefits in large-scale environments.

In terms of performance, the application of CODECO is expected to improve scalability, resilience, and availability in comparison to Kubernetes, while providing support for mobile environments.

Figure 8: AGVs (Automated Guided Vehicles) for Flexible Factories Use Case.

2.4.6 P6: Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings (Energy)

The use case focuses on novel mechanisms for automated deployments of smart office / smart building applications on the Crownstone Platform, a novel positioning platform developed by one of the CODECO partners. In this context, an application is defined as a collection of related functionalities realized by means of a set of interconnected application components which can run either in the Cloud, on the Crownstone Hub, or inside a Crownstone Node.

Figure 9: A CODECO P6 high-level representation.

The key issue addressed is how the CODECO technologies can help with automated deployment of multiple applications on the Crownstone platform, both in single cluster situations (i.e., with multiple Crownstone Hubs form a single manageable entity with a single user base), and in multi-cluster situations (i.e. with multiple Crownstone Hubs form multiple manageable entities with different but potentially overlapping) user bases).

The Crownstone platform technology has been developed within the Almende group during the past years.

The Microapp deployment architecture illustrated in Figure 9 can be divided in a Cloud level, a local (per building/apartment) level and IoT level. Crownstone are already administered in spheres. A sphere is a collection of Crownstones with associated locations (e.g., rooms) and users. A digital twin of this representation is present in the Crownstone Cloud.

2.5 More Information and How to Engage

For more information about the CODECO project:

- Visit the project's Website: <https://he-codeco.eu/> and engage via the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement (IRCEP) Programme.
- Follow CODECO on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/codeco-project/>
- Visit the demonstrations and use-cases videos in the CODECO YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@CODECOPROJECT>
- Check the publications and presentations available in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco/>
- Download the open-source code and experiment with the CODECO Experimentation Framework: <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/>

3 COGNIFOG: Cognitive, Self-Aware, AI-based Edge Cloud Management

3.1 Overview

Cognitive-Fog is the concept enabling the IoT-to-Edge-to-Cloud continuum. Despite its heterogeneous nature, the fog side allows dynamic resource allocation and sharing at many sub-layers between the Cloud and the Edge. In the IoT side, it provides interoperability facilities so that IoT devices can be easily connected to the continuum and communicate with other Edge-side components. On the Edge side, it can be hosted on micro servers, where it operates as an extension of the centralised Cloud. On the Cloud side, it will help to orchestrate all necessary resources so that an end-to-end service is provided in a safe and secure way and in both directions. Such technology, covering all these aspects, does not exist and needs to be designed and developed.

COGNIFOG provides an efficient tool that will facilitate the orchestration of heterogeneous distributed computing resources in a wide where IoT, Edge and Cloud ecosystem could interact and build a harmonized fog continuum. COGNIFOG framework provides distinct, loosely coupled tools, each addressing specific functionalities vital to the continuum.

COGNIFOG allows the deployment of applications at different levels (far Edge, near Edge, and Cloud). The modelling tools will enable the description of various applications in various domains. The orchestrator allows the workload to be distributed automatically in a Kubernetes multi-cluster environment according to the application's needs. A comprehensive monitoring stack has been developed and integrated, enabling real-time monitoring and management of the system's performance and health. A multi-cluster orchestrator manages applications and services across multiple clusters, spanning on-premises, hybrid, and multi-Cloud environments while mitigating complexity, enhancing scalability, ensuring resilience, and bolstering security and compliance. The interoperability is smoothly ensured between Cloud and Edge levels and between Edge and IoT levels. Finally, QoS Solver mainly considers energy efficiency and sustainability to realise energy-efficient placement.

COGNIFOG framework is validated on three different domains: coordinated crisis management in urban areas (Thales); E-health services in the Edge-Cloud continuum (TMA) and Automated Edge-Cloud continuum for Smart Manufacturing (LMS).

3.2 Unique Value Proposition

COGNIFOG framework provides distinct, loosely coupled tools, each addressing specific functionalities vital to the continuum. First, it ensures interoperability at the IoT Edge and Edge-Cloud levels. The loosely coupled tools and the adoption of open standards, which are widely accepted in industry, ensure adaptability. The tools can be integrated into various configurations, tailored to suit the unique demands of different use cases. The architecture is composed of independent modules or components. Each module handles a distinct functionality and is composed together; they will constitute the entire system. This **modularity** ensures that it can be done without disrupting the whole system if there is a need to update or replace a particular module. By providing well-defined API endpoints and communication protocols, different tools within COGNIFOG can be integrated into various configurations. This ensures that the architecture can be tailored to specific use cases, offering a level of customisation crucial in addressing unique challenges or requirements. In addition, different monitoring tools allow the collection of system performance metrics. This data will refine and optimise the architecture, even during system execution.

3.3 Technical Architecture

COGNIFOG framework is multidimensional and covers the entire life cycle of a workload from design and development to execution and data generation. A typical user of COGNIFOG should be able to use its different services to design, prepare, execute, and monitor its workload in the most secure, agile, and efficient way. The building blocks provided by the partners have been gathered and classified in four vertical layers:

1. The modelling layer where the design and architecture of the software take shape. It is composed of the different tools dedicated to the topology description with software and hardware requirements, SLA models, application data-flow models and the infrastructure models. The primary objective here is to provide the users with tools to abstractly define and design the system before it is built, allowing for better system optimization, cost and energy efficiency and planning for future update and/or scalability. These tools will also help to set better expectations regarding the performance, uptime, and other operational aspects of a service.
2. The DevOps layer includes the tools and practices designed to automate and streamline the software development and deployment process. These tools will provide a CI/CD framework to the user to automatically compile and test code changes (CI) and automatically deploy changes to the production environment (CD). For COGNIFOG, we chose to use the well-known open-source tools for better cost-efficiency, interoperability, transparency, and flexibility. To complement these tools and boost efficiency, security, development, integration and deployment methodologies and best practices are also provided.
3. The runtime layer: where the software applications run. The runtime layer includes the actual environments where applications operate, be it on-premises, in the Cloud, on Edge devices or anywhere in the fog. It encompasses servers, operating systems, containers, serverless environments, databases, and other essential components necessary to host and run the application. This layer provides all the required components to ensure that the user's workload performs efficiently, scales appropriately, and remains stable during operations.
4. The governance layer includes tools and practices for smart orchestration, monitoring, logging, auditing, and reporting. This layer will ensure that the right processes are followed, the policies are enforced, the software is secure, data is protected, and any issues can be traced and rectified.

Figure 10: The COGNIFOG Architecture.

The COGNIFOG components have been also classified according to their functionalities:

- **Infrastructure management:** This encompasses the foundational tools and systems responsible for setting up, managing, and maintaining the Cloud-to-Edge-to-IoT infrastructure. It involves the entire process of modelling the infrastructure in a design phase, automating its deployment, and then establishing the connectivity across devices, Edge nodes, and Cloud systems.
- **Monitoring tools:** COGNIFOG monitoring tools keep track of the health, performance, and status of the infrastructure, network, and applications. They provide real-time insights into system operations, detect anomalies, and can trigger alerts or corrective actions.
- **Security tools:** This category includes the tools and solutions responsible for safeguarding the infrastructure and the data flow. Security tools ensure that data remains confidential, system integrity is maintained, and services are available without interruptions, making the COGNIFOG stack trustworthy and reliable.
- **Application toolbox:** This category focuses on enabling interoperability for the user's applications, ensuring that different devices, systems, and platforms can communicate and work together effectively. The tools here might address data format conversions, protocol translations, middleware solutions, etc.

3.4 Validating Use Cases

3.4.1 Collaborative Missions in Urban Areas

Centennial floods, which occur once every hundred years, can cause significant disruption to urban infrastructure, as seen in cities like Paris. These extreme events overwhelm transportation and communication systems, making roads and railways impassable and isolating communities. Damaged communication networks further hinder emergency responses, underscoring the need for more resilient infrastructure and effective flood management strategies.

In flood emergencies, timely intervention by authorities is crucial, requiring effective synchronization between rescue teams. Current systems, however, face challenges due to the limitations of existing architecture, which is not designed to handle critical factors like network congestion, latency, and the automatic re-provisioning of applications during disruptions. This reliance on standard scheduling policies, such as CPU and RAM usage, leaves the system vulnerable during connectivity failures.

Edge computing without intelligent workload placement exacerbates these issues, leading to inefficient resource use, higher latency, increased power consumption, and network congestion. The lack of dynamic adaptability in workload distribution reduces scalability, system reliability, and real-time processing capabilities. In flood scenarios, this inefficiency impacts low-latency applications, making the system more costly, less effective, and prone to failure.

The requirements for a collaborative mission use case on a COGNIFOG platform emphasize deployment automation across Edge and far-Edge environments to ensure consistency, scalability, and security. This enables organizations like rescue centres to swiftly deploy software and applications, responding more effectively to changing needs. Rapid infrastructure and device provisioning is essential during disasters, supporting real-time situational awareness. Fast Cloud application deployments reduce downtime, enhance scalability, and improve cost efficiency. Time predictability and resiliency to hardware or connectivity failures ensure operational stability and continuity during emergencies. Additionally, energy consumption monitoring is crucial for reliability and sustainability, while

single-touch orchestration allows seamless deployment and management of applications with minimal effort.

3.4.2 E-Health Services in the Edge-Cloud Continuum

This use case is provided by Telematic Medical Applications (TMA). TMA is a leading healthcare systems integrator and value-added solutions provider in computer science-based healthcare systems. The use case is based on a real business use case from a large TMA customer in the construction industry. The customer is involved in large construction sites in Greece and in setting up and servicing wind turbines. These construction projects frequently employ hundreds of personnel who work in rural and remote areas, which presents unique challenges in terms of safety and health monitoring.

The primary requirement is to ensure the safety of the personnel through continuous monitoring and to provide a first-response telemedicine solution in case of emergencies. In such environments, workers are exposed to various hazards, including accidents, injuries, and health issues exacerbated by the lack of immediate medical facilities. These challenges can be addressed with the implementation of a robust telemedicine solution. This system must be capable of real-time monitoring of workers' vital signs, immediate detection of health anomalies, and quick initiation of medical consultations.

TMA's products can effectively address the scenario. These include portable telemedicine systems that can be deployed on-site, wearable health monitoring devices for personnel, and a Cloud-based platform for data analysis and communication with medical staff. The portable telemedicine systems, designed as rugged and self-contained units, can be equipped with various medical sensors to conduct accurate health assessments. These systems facilitate real-time video consultations with medical professionals, ensuring workers receive timely medical advice and intervention. Wearable devices such as smartwatches can monitor vital signs like heart rate, blood oxygen levels, and physical activity. They also provide safety features like fall detection and SOS alerts, essential in hazardous work environments. The collected data is transmitted via secure, private networks established on-site, ensuring reliable communication even in areas with limited mobile network coverage. By utilising these advanced telemedicine solutions, the customer can ensure a safer working environment and prompt medical response, significantly reducing the risk of severe health incidents and improving overall operational efficiency.

The COGNIFOG platform requirements for the Telemedicine use case emphasize autonomous deployment and management of Edge and IoT systems to ensure consistency, scalability, and reliability. Rapid infrastructure setup is essential, enabling fast provisioning of IoT devices and telemedicine suitcases, ensuring that the Cloud-to-Edge-to-IoT system becomes operational quickly. Quick deployment of network services is critical for maintaining efficiency, while resilience to hardware and connectivity issues is necessary for continuous operation. Enhanced data security is achieved by processing sensitive information locally at the Edge, with encrypted backups sent to the Cloud daily. The system must support high device connectivity, handling over 100 IoT devices per Edge server, ensuring scalability and reliability. Additionally, the platform should allow multi-cluster deployments, enabling replication of trial setups based on configuration changes.

3.4.3 Automated Edge-Cloud Continuum for Smart Manufacturing

The manufacturing scenario provided by the Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems & Automation (LMS) in Greece involves the collaboration of a mobile robot equipped with a collaborative arm, alongside two additional robots tasked with transportation. The mobile robot supports an operator in the assembly process, while the other two robots handle the transportation of materials to the workstation. Each robot operates with its own ROS (Robot Operating System) application, collaborating to complete the assembly on time. Task scheduling plays a vital role in ensuring the timely transportation of parts, and in case of failure of one transportation robot, the other must take over both tasks to maintain the workflow. While the assembly robot is a real mobile robot, the transportation robots are simulated.

The smart manufacturing scenario presents several challenges that could be addressed through the integration of COGNIFOG technologies. Given the scenario's requirement for seamless interaction between multiple devices, efficient cooperation and control of both hardware and software components is crucial. Additionally, dynamic deployment across all devices and applications, which rely on ROS channels for data exchange, is necessary. Security for data and networks is another key concern. Furthermore, the increased connection of devices to a single network introduces challenges related to latency and data storage capacity, which need to be addressed.

From a technical perspective, intelligent orchestration, dynamic deployment, and high-level coordination are challenges that can be addressed using COGNIFOG components. In simple manufacturing scenarios, each robot uses its own ROS infrastructure, typically utilizing Edge resources to minimize delays, though Cloud deployment may be necessary for more complex coordination tasks. Centralized coordination also introduces a requirement for innovative and dynamic deployment setups, which can be managed through Kubernetes (Kubernetes) cluster deployments. Robots must first be implemented as ROS containers, deployed on Kubernetes clusters, and then managed by COGNIFOG components. However, deploying multiple robots under the same infrastructure could pose challenges related to network bandwidth or storage capacity, requiring careful consideration.

3.5 More Information and How to Engage

To follow up COGNIFOG's recent activities and latest news:

- Visit the official website: <https://cognifog.eu/> where the public deliverables and publications as well as upcoming events and latest news are announced.
- Subscribe to COGNIFOG LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cognifogproject> where latest news are announced.
- Subscribe to COGNIFOG's YouTube Channel: www.youtube.com/@cognifogproject where webinars and COGNIFOG's videos are published.

4 COGNIT: A Serverless Approach for Sovereign Edge Cloud Management

4.1 Overview

Multi-provider Cloud-Edge Continuum is overly complex – particularly when considering properties such as multiple providers, heterogeneous hardware, dynamic changes in utilization, pricing. Developing native applications for such environments is a significant challenge for application developers, requiring a high amount of training and infrastructure knowledge. The *Serverless* paradigm is rapidly growing in popularity, as it mitigates this complexity - developers deploy individual functions to a Continuum, which are then managed by the providers themselves.

The COGNIT project aims to integrate AI technology into Cloud-Edge management systems to create a European sovereign *cognitive Cloud reference framework and associated tools with a particular aim of supporting serverless functions*. Specifically, COGNIT work towards:

1. Supporting an innovative new serverless paradigm for Edge application management and enhanced digital sovereignty for users and developers.
2. Enabling on-demand deployment of large-scale, highly distributed, and self-adaptive serverless environments using existing Cloud resources.
3. Optimizing data placement according to changes in energy efficiency heuristics and application demands and behavior.
4. Enabling secure and trusted execution of serverless runtimes.

The project features 10 partners from 6 countries and is informed and validated through four use case partners, spanning the domains of traffic management, cyber-security, wildfire management, and energy systems.

4.2 Unique Value Proposition

COGNIT is addressing several unresolved research challenges related to the application of Serverless technology to Cognitive Cloud Continuums. These include:

- **Function Management.** COGNIT is extending the disaggregated Cloud management model for virtualized environments to manage the execution of serverless Runtimes on highly distributed data processing environments, with a full DevOps approach for infrastructure.
- **Seamless user access and programming models.** COGNIT is developing a new distributed serverless model that, when integrated with a Cognitive management platform, facilitates the development of elastic and scalable Edge-based applications.
- **New Serverless functionalities.** COGNIT provides new functionalities to manage dynamicity and heterogeneity at the Cloud-Edge, the need to distribute computing and storage capabilities across a variety of providers, and the integration of special-purpose Cloud and Edge locations and services needed by the use cases.
- **Deployment and migration of serverless functions.** COGNIT is developing techniques and mechanisms for creating a software overlay that enables the deployment and migration of serverless functions across Edge Points of Presence, and their self-adaptive execution with vertical scale up/down to adapt capacity to data processing needs.
- **AI modules and optimization techniques.** COGNIT is developing scalable, multi-variate AI-enabled modeling and optimization techniques that function in large-scale,

serverless, continuum environments. The project is also creating new methods to rapidly create and retrain ML-based predictive behavioral forecasts for all major management considerations faced by Cloud-Edge continuum environments, whilst minimizing creation/retraining latency.

- **Energy efficiency and adaptation to green energy.** COGNIT is developing: 1) Heuristics and metrics for evaluating energy and sustainability performance; 2) Data-driven ML methods for profiling compute nodes and workloads; 3) A grid-aware hierarchical multi-constraint (temporal, latency, etc.) management layer to allocate workloads; and 4) A holistic study of energy performance evaluation taking into account the whole Cloud-Edge energy life cycle.
- **Secure and trusted execution of computing environments.** COGNIT is developing methods for security at the orchestration layer across the Continuum, including global Cloud-Edge security policies, orchestration-level constraints, and reasoning to securely place Serverless functions based on location and trusted/confidential computing constraints. The project is also investigating the use of confidential and trusted computing to secure computation of confidential data at the Edge or in the Cloud, and federated learning techniques for low latency and privacy-respecting anomaly detection of serverless services.

4.3 Technical Architecture

The main management unit of the COGNIT Framework where to provision Serverless Runtime is the **Edge Cluster** - a semi-autonomous compute environment with a dedicated software-defined resource set (compute, network, and storage) able to work on unreliable infrastructures. Given the heterogeneity of Cloud-Edge systems, the Edge Cluster creates an abstraction layer enabling interoperability across the multi-provider Cloud-Edge infrastructure. Major components are illustrated in Figure 11 and described next.

Figure 11: Main Components of the COGNIT Framework.

- **Cognit Frontend:** This component is the main entry point for the COGNIT service. It authenticates and authorizes device clients that would like to use the service. It then queries the AI-Orchestrator for the “optimal” Edge Cluster where the device can offload the execution of the functions. It returns to the Device Runtime the Edge Cluster Frontend endpoint.

- **Device Client:** This is a library/User API to define application requirements, execute functions and upload data using Cloud-Edge continuum resources.
- **Device Runtime:** This component allows a device to execute functions on the Cloud-Edge Continuum. In conjunction with the Device Client, it provides the user application everything needed to interact with COGNIT.
- **Provisioning Engine:** This component is responsible for managing the lifecycle of the Serverless Runtimes; it can create, delete, and update the Serverless Runtimes according to the operations that are sent by the Device.
- **Cloud-Edge Manager:** The CEM is responsible for managing the highly distributed and heterogeneous resources of the Cloud-Edge continuum to schedule Serverless Runtimes according to the device/applications requirements.
- **AI-Enabled Orchestrator:** The major “cognitive” component within the project, the AI-O is responsible for producing an initial deployment plan according to the device requirements. It will update the deployment plan in case of updated requirements sent by the device, but will also dynamically optimize the Serverless Runtime placement, taking into account the monitoring of the resources (e.g. VMs, networks, etc.) used by the Serverless Runtime and the application metrics (e.g. application workload) sent by the Serverless Runtime. The orchestrator intelligently proposes changes to application and hardware infrastructure according to optimization criteria. It manages infrastructure through provisioning the Edge Clusters and their provisioned resources (e.g., servers) and manages applications through provisioning the serverless function compute unit (Serverless Runtimes) at Edge Clusters, and through mapping Device Clients to Edge Clusters. Optimization criteria are multi-objective and can include aspects such as application-driven demands (e.g., request frequency, latency, GPU access) and environmentally driven (e.g., cost, energy efficiency, green-energy availability).

4.4 Validating Use Cases

COGNIT is working with four use case partners to not only motivate the work but to assess the effectiveness of the final system in production environments. These use cases are drawn from the domains of Smart Cities, Agriculture and Environment, Energy, and Cybersecurity.

4.5 Use Case 1 | Smart Cities

A novel solution for public transport priority management is being evaluated that combines next generation Traffic Light Controllers (TLC), with COGNIT's cognitive serverless framework to automate and conduct intelligent resource provisioning across the continuum based on QoS requirements. The COGNIT Smart City use case will gather and process data from traffic detectors, the speed, location, and direction of surrounding vehicles reported through C-V2X messages, bus schedule delays published by public transport management systems, weather conditions. This information comes from different systems, through different channels and protocols, at different cadences, and must be processed in a matter of milliseconds to give the TLC enough time to safely adjust the timings of traffic lights.

Furthermore, existing low-fidelity city models employed in traffic management mostly rely on centralized systems, with limited capacity to assess real-world scenarios with high accuracy and low latency. This can be improved by performing computation as close to a vehicle requestor as possible, relying on COGNIT to abstract parts of the traffic management & public transport systems from the operations, nodes and communications used to achieve the result.

4.6 Use Case 2: Wildfire Detection | Energy/Climate

Using a traditional Cloud model, latency and near-real-time analytics on the behavior and spread of wildfires cannot be achieved effectively due to the large amount of information transmitted. Using data processing capabilities of Edge applications closer to response teams deployed on the ground can provide a powerful tool for real-time assessment of wildfires.

Despite the rapid emergence of a new generation of devices and optimized coding libraries, processing capabilities of environmental sensors are still limited and their deployment in remote areas requires low energy consumption.

COGNIT is prototyping a distributed network for real-time wildfire detection combining Nature 4.0 sensors with the cognitive serverless framework. A new AI-powered Edge application will be deployed on the devices, leveraging next-generation Arm Cortex M7 ultra-low-power microprocessors and micro python AI libraries, and making use of the Cloud-Edge continuum through an FaaS model to reduce latency time for processing real-time data and testing how to build a sustainable and secure service for local civil protection teams.

4.7 Use Case 3 | Energy

Due to diminishing energy resources (oil, gas, carbon) it is critical to develop solutions for individual energy independence of a household and/or small energy clusters. This necessitates the development of methods for monitoring, predicting, and managing both energy production and consumption in each environment. For this, the implementation of smart Edge applications that make use of advanced AI/ML algorithms is needed.

COGNIT is designing and evaluating a new Edge application deployment model based on providing an energy production/consumption prediction service. This model will leverage the Project's cognitive serverless framework to allow AI/ML algorithms to offload workloads to the Cloud-Edge continuum by combining the application execution environment in energy meters with the new FaaS engine. Data produced by the "Edge-IoT Meter" will monitor energy consumption, detect anomalies, and optimize energy usage.

4.8 Use Case 4 | Cybersecurity

Moving computation and data processing services to the Edge, far from secured datacenters, leaves systems exposed to new threats. Solutions, especially those based on AI/ML algorithms, benefit from being able to leverage additional resources on-demand across the continuum - and must be assessed and tightly integrated with those container management technologies that dominate the market, especially with platforms based on Kubernetes.

COGNIT is designing and assessing a use case focused on securing the development and operation of an FaaS workflow on a smart mobility solution at the Edge. A DevSecOps pipeline is being implemented that integrates development, operations, and security activities to update and operate software deployed on simulated and physical autonomous rovers based on the Robot Operating System and the Kubeedge framework. This approach focuses on providing distributed anomaly detection at the Edge, applying confidential computing to protect data in the rovers not only at rest or in transit but also in use (during runtime), and will orchestrate the security response using the Vaccine SOAR (Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response) platform based on security policies.

Anomaly detection must be distributed to collect data from the entire attack surface of the rover system that includes not only the rovers themselves operating in a platoon, but also the Cloud/Edge-based traffic supervision system. The aim of distributed anomaly is to detect the anomalous behavior due to the intrusion as early as possible before the damage is done, e.g., by fault injection to cause rovers to crash.

4.9 More Information and How to Engage

The COGNIT project involves 10 partners from 6 countries. The project is coordinated by OpenNebula Systems and funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, under Grant Agreement. More information can be found at <https://cognit.sovereignedge.eu/> or by contacting Scientific Coordinator, Dr. Paul Townend (paul.townend@umu.se).

5 MLSYSOPS: Autonomic, Efficient, and Adaptive Edge-Cloud-IoT System Management

5.1 Overview – Motivation – Challenge

The advent of Cloud-Edge-IoT computing aggravates the challenging task of managing heterogeneous and distributed resources, this time at an extreme scale, making human-in-the-loop management completely unrealistic. Beyond scale and heterogeneity, the high dynamicity, and intrinsic local properties/variability of the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum yield rule-based approaches – traditionally used in autonomic systems – insufficient. AI-driven management is a promising alternative, although the quest to extend this to the full continuum faces similar challenges. An additional roadblock towards the widespread adoption of AI for system management is the lack of transparency and explainability taken by ML models.

The MLSysOps project addresses these challenges to enable autonomic, efficient, and adaptive end-to-end system management on the heterogeneous and dynamic Edge-Cloud-IoT continuum. To this end, MLSysOps (i) disassociates the management from the control of continuum resources, (ii) introduces an AI-driven control and management framework that interfaces with off-the-shelf management mechanisms, (iii) employs a hierarchical, distributed, explainable, and evolving AI architecture for autonomic system operation, (iv) supports the flexible addition and usage of ML models for different system management problems and layers.

5.2 Conceptual View and Main actors

The MLSysOps framework receives application and infrastructure descriptions, as well as the intents of applications and the optimization targets of platform administrators. An AI-driven, MAPE-based manager incrementally refines these high-level requirements to concrete control commands, eventually issued to different underlying resource management mechanisms across the layers of the continuum. Throughout operation, telemetry data are collected which, in turn, enables the system's situational awareness and evolution. Figure 12 illustrates the conceptual view of MLSysOps.

The main actors and their interaction with the MLSysOps framework are:

- **Application Developer.** Develops the application that will run in the infrastructure and prepares the application description according to the respective MLSysOps syntax, capturing the application's components, resource requirements, interactions, placement directives/preferences/affinities, and QoS targets. The application developer uses the MLSysOps application Telemetry API so that application components can push application-level performance/QoS information to the framework.
- **Application Administrator.** Submits the application description for execution to the MLSysOps framework, monitors its performance, and is notified about the deployment and configuration decisions taken by the framework. The interaction with the MLSysOps framework occurs via the Northbound API. The role of the application developer and application administrator can often be assumed by the same entity.
- **Infrastructure Provider & System Administrator.** Provides the physical system infrastructure/nodes controlled by MLSysOps. The nodes can span the continuum, ranging from powerful Cloud nodes to lightweight far-Edge nodes. The provider prepares the description for each part of the infrastructure according to the MLSysOps system description syntax, capturing the types of nodes, their resources, and available system-level services. The system administrator also sets the desired system optimization targets and monitors system resource usage and system-level management/configuration

decisions. The corresponding interaction with the MLSysOps framework also occurs via the Northbound API.

- **ML model provider.** Provides and updates (e.g., after offline training) machine-learning models employed by the MLSysOps framework to take specific system management/configuration decisions. The corresponding interaction with the MLSysOps framework occurs via the Side API.

Figure 12: MLSysOps concept.

5.3 Technical Architecture

Figure 13 illustrates the internal organization of the MLSysOps framework. The core of MLSysOps is a hierarchical agent system, which interacts with the other two pillars of the framework: container orchestration and telemetry. The agent hierarchy follows the orchestration architecture, which is logically organized into three levels. Communication between the three subsystems (agents, container orchestration, and telemetry) is managed through appropriate interfaces at every level. All three subsystems have internal communication across various levels, while the agent communicates with the system actors at the continuum (highest) level. At the node level, the agent employs a controller to execute the commands for low-level configuration knobs.

MLSysOps accomplishes the management by using telemetry data that is emitted from every level to attain the necessary insights while using machine learning models for decision-making at each level. Agents propagate and refine decisions from top to bottom. The overall status and results of the decisions become available to System Actors. Similarly, telemetry information is summarized bottom-up, resulting in actionable metrics, at different granularities for various levels of the system.

Figure 13: MLSysOps architecture.

The main challenge the MLSysOps framework needs to address is system resource management as well as scheduling, deployment, and orchestration of application components. A suitable hierarchical AI/ML architecture consumes telemetry data and makes application orchestration and platform configuration decisions at each level, enabling high efficiency and adaptability in the dynamic Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. ML models identify drift and exploit slack in application execution to enable continual model retraining.

Another important aspect of the ML architecture in MLSysOps is its modular design. The Side API, a well-defined interface between agents and ML models, enables the registration, deployment, invocation and retraining of different machine learning models developed by external developers.

Moreover, the ML models in MLSysOps are designed to enable the explainability of ML decisions. Explanations can be produced offline, using stored telemetry data and logs, and are made available to system operators.

5.4 Validating Use Cases

5.4.1 Smart Agriculture

On-field solutions for precise agriculture such as “Augmenta Mantis,” disrupt traditional agriculture practices; the system can decide and apply individualized care of crops according to their perceived needs, reducing the use of chemicals such as fertilizers and pesticides. MLSysOps will extend the commercial on-field system solution by Augmenta, by adding a real-time scanning system using autonomous UAVs to add a vertical, birds-eye perspective to the horizontal perspective provided by on-tractor cameras. The system will selectively deploy the drone, according to current conditions and available battery capacity, intelligently partitioning the computational pipeline between the on-tractor device and the drones.

Figure 14: MLSysOps agriculture use-case, sensing aspects.

5.4.2 Smart cities

The goal of a smart city is to leverage technology and data to enhance the quality of life for its citizens and visitors, while also improving the efficiency and sustainability of urban infrastructures and services. Cities can use real-time data from CCTV cameras and other sensors either stationary or mobile (e.g., noise, pollution, temperature, humidity) to better understand the liveliness of the city. Having a large-scale distributed system of sensors and computer units allows city operators to analyze how traffic patterns change, identify emergencies, provide faster response, and produce complex analytics.

Figure 15: MLSysOps smart cities use-case, sensing aspects.

Manually managing such Cloud-Edge infrastructure is cumbersome. It requires a full view of the system status and goals provided by the authorities, and high-level technical knowledge to understand and deal with this complex technological ecosystem. MLSysOps will alleviate the management burden, as well as improve system efficiency.

5.5 More Information and How to Engage

For more information you can access MLSysOps web site (<https://mlsysops.eu/>) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/mlsysops/>).

6 ENACT: Optimized Allocation of Cloud Edge HPC Workloads

6.1 Overview

The emergence of high-performance Edge devices along with the wider availability of Cloud and HPC facilities present new opportunities for the distributed deployment and execution of data-intensive applications across the computing continuum. However, the diversity of computer resources and managing the applications execution needs across heterogeneous resources also introduce new challenges.

ENACT aims to address such challenges by offering solutions tailored to meet the special needs of the Cloud-Edge Continuum, such as solutions that support the modelling and management of (Cloud and Edge) resources, and solutions that support the dynamic scaling, elasticity, and portability of hyper-distributed data-intensive applications. To realize the ENACT vision, the project builds upon recent technological advancements in the areas of zero-touch provisioning, AI scheduling and optimization algorithms, Graphic Neural Networks, virtual AI training techniques, application-level adaptation techniques and Data Spaces. The developed concepts and technological solutions will be tested and validated in three pilot domains, where distributed applications are expected to make significant economic and ecologic impacts.

6.2 Unique Value Proposition

ENACT's overarching goal is to create a highly adaptable Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) that optimizes the performance of data-intensive applications distributed across the Edge and Cloud resources. Towards this goal, ENACT provides a holistic platform that brings together innovative concepts and technological solutions to enable continuous network and infrastructure monitoring, dynamic graph-based modelling, real-time risk assessment, automated resource provisioning, sovereign data management as well as cognitive scheduling and orchestration of distributed applications. ENACT supports the realization of CCC at both the infrastructure level and at the application level.

At the infrastructure level, ENACT supports dynamic networking of Edge-Cloud resources using Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) as a programmable network fabric. Based on the availability of the distributed resources, ENACT allows for real-time visibility and connections of distributed resources through Dynamic Graph Models that capture and visualize real-time and historical status, node connectivity, dependencies, and energy consumption across diverse and distributed Edge and Cloud resources. The dynamic graph models are continuously updated based on the ZTP-enabled automatic resource (re-)configurations and bespoke telemetry data collection service. Moreover, graph models are subsequently used by AI-based Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) agents, which suggest optimal deployment configurations for hyper-distributed applications. The deployment configurations are verified through Security Risk Assessment before they are used in an intelligent decision-making engine that can replace the scheduling components of existing Kubernetes-like solutions. Equipped with cognitive decision-making capabilities, the resulting AI-powered scheduler supports a multistage optimization process which harnesses the power of AI to progressively refine and update the scheduling plans based on network status, node availability, communication bandwidth and energy consumption, eventually optimizing resource utilisation and task allocation for distributed applications.

At the application, ENACT develops an innovative Application Programming Model (APM) that provides readily available software libraries, functions and guidelines to support the development of adaptive applications, capable of monitoring their performance and suggesting adaptation actions (to the scheduler) to assist in their optimal deployment and

optimal execution across the diverse resources available within the CCC. The use of APM is supported by a Software Development Kit (SDK) that provides the application development and testing environment to facilitate the development of more intelligent and adaptive applications or enhancement of existing applications with features available through APM.

6.3 Technical Architecture

Figure 16 illustrates the ENACT reference architecture, which consists of five interoperating layers.

Figure 16: ENACT Technical Architecture.

- The **Orchestration Layer** is responsible for automatically configuring different types of Edge and Cloud resources through the *ZTP service* to help establish the Edge-Cloud continuum. The interconnected infrastructure is constantly monitored via the *Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine*. A key component in this layer is the cognitive *Orchestrator* that is responsible for optimizing the orchestration and deployment of applications and services on suitable resources, spanning from the Edge to the Cloud.
- The **Modelling Layer** is responsible for modelling the distributed resources and bringing necessary visibility to the distributed resources. Innovative *Dynamic Graph Modelling* techniques are used to not only allow for greater visibility of available resources but also to their connections and dependencies.
- The **AI Layer** analyses the dynamic graph models using *AI-enabled Forecasting* mechanisms, *Graph Neural Networks* and *Deep Reinforcement Learning* techniques to determine the best deployment configurations for distributed applications. The AI models are continuously trained and updated in a dedicated *Virtual Training Environment* and *Security Risk Modelling* is performed to analyse and mitigate risks associated with suggested application deployment configurations.

- The **Data Layer** implements the Data Space concept to support the AI models by securely storing telemetry and AI-related data and ensuring its sovereignty in the distributed infrastructure.
- The **App Development Layer** implements the *Application Programming Model*. An *Application Controller* component (prescribed in the APM) allows applications to self-determine the required adaptation policies to achieve their optimal deployment based on the analysis of resource monitoring data and the application performance.

6.4 Validating Use Cases

The ENACT technological outcomes will be validated in three pilot domains, each one corresponding to a distinct use case involving hyper-distributed data-intensive applications. For example, the media streaming use case, led by MOG Technologies, focuses on the processing of multimedia data in the sports event broadcasting domain. This use-case focuses on a highly time-critical application where the drop in the performance of the application may compromise the broadcasting services for the end client. ENACT's technological advancements introduce benefits for the media streaming use case in terms of performance, security, as well as business and environmental impact. Facilitating dynamic deployment of computing tasks across the ENACT CCC Edge devices and Cloud servers and distributed data processing enables uninterrupted broadcasting and intelligent video annotation, resulting in enhanced streaming performance. Given that proprietary data flows through the streaming pipeline, data access controls and authentication mechanisms become pivotal to safeguard the system against unauthorised access and data breaches. Therefore, ENACT's security mechanisms contribute to protecting intellectual property and cultivate stakeholder trust. From a business perspective, ENACT enhances the value proposition for customers. Leveraging the continuum effectively translates into tangible cost savings, minimising infrastructure overheads and maximising performance. The ENACT solutions enable the optimisation of resource utilisation and reducing operational costs for media broadcasting companies, such as MOG, allowing them to bolster their competitiveness and market positioning. Finally, ENACT's energy-aware task placement results in optimized resource allocation in terms of energy efficiency. This optimisation prioritises environmental sustainability allowing the application to capitalise on the growing market demand for sustainable solutions, thereby enhancing MOG's brand reputation and market positioning. Another example of ENACT validation is the deployment and management of FUJITSU's Digital Twin platform that is designed for real-time monitoring and simulation of behaviours in urban environments. In this use case, FUJITSU's Digital Twin Dracena platform and the Integra visualization tool will be integrated with a variety of data sources and systems that collect and process real-time data from IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems among others to provide a powerful solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimization of urban environments. Overall, a city's Digital Twin supported by ENACT will provide a real-time operational view of the urban environment to enable data-driven decision-making and smart, proactive management of city resources and services, ultimately leading to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators. For example, a city Digital Twin could ingest real-time air pollution data from sensors across the city and use advanced data analytics and ML models to identify pollution hotspots, predict pollution levels, evaluate the impact of policy changes, and optimise traffic flows to minimise emissions. The integration of the Digital Twin and ENACT technologies has perceived advantages of reduced data duplications and optimised data distribution. Leveraging Edge computing and distributed storage mechanisms to place data closer to the points of consumption, minimises redundant data duplications, storage costs, retrieval latency and network congestion, while ensuring critical data replicability and availability. In addition, ENACT's hyper-distributed architecture allows for the optimal utilisation of computing resources, load balancing, and scalability. Moreover, through ENACT, the data processing

tasks can be intelligently partitioned and assigned to different nodes based on their capabilities, locality, and workload characteristics. This will enable the Digital Twin platform to handle the growing volume, velocity, and variety of data generated providing real-time insights and actionable intelligence.

6.5 More Information and How to Engage

To follow up ENACT's recent activities and latest news:

- Visit the official website: <https://enact-horizon.eu/>, wherein the upcoming events and latest news are announced. More information about the project scope and objectives is also available here.
- Visit, watch and star the Gitlab repository (maintained by Eclipse): <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project>, to inspect the project's open-source solutions.
- Subscribe to ENACT's YouTube Channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@ENACT-INNO>, wherein key ENACT presentations can be found.

ENACT members also participate actively in several scientific venues (e.g. conferences, workshops and panel discussions) to communicate the project mission and results.

7 DECICE: Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration framework

7.1 Overview

In the past decade, Cloud computing has revolutionized computing by providing services over the internet that can scale elastically for user requirements. The economics of scale have resulted in not only improved productivity, reliability but also reduction in cost and enhanced security. The growth of data, network and compute technologies along with the requirement for mobile end devices, faster response time and compliance with data privacy and protection regulations has driven the advance of Edge computing as an extension of Cloud computing. For users of applications like Data analytics, Smart home/city, Industrial automation and others, Edge computing provides mobility, location awareness, ultra-low latency, and proximity. Edge computing complements Cloud services running on the internet, by providing limited services (compute) at the Edge network and thereby reducing jitter, probability of attacks.

The unique and advantageous characteristics of Edge computing come with new challenges for cluster management due to the heterogeneity of computing elements and widespread networks. There are requirements for optimizing the utilization of available resources (reducing data traffic between Cloud and Edge), improving the scalability and reliability of distributed applications, giving local autonomy to Edge resources (offline processing and self-recovery) and enhancing the privacy and security of user data and applications. This not only requires management of Cloud and Edge infrastructure elements (like compute, storage and network) but also sophisticated application deployment and data movement/placement. With rising cost of energy, it is imperative that clusters strive to improve the energy efficiency and utilization of Cloud and Edge resources.

The Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration framework addresses the emerging demands and challenges of modern computing, specifically within the continuum from centralized Cloud infrastructures to distributed Edge devices. As applications increasingly rely on both Cloud and Edge resources for their computational and data needs, there is a critical need for a cohesive management framework that can handle the complexity, heterogeneity, and scalability of such environments. This project seeks to create an adaptable, AI-driven framework that autonomously optimizes application deployment and resource allocation across high-performance computing (HPC) centers, Cloud platforms, and Edge networks.

7.2 Technical Architecture

In its holistic design, the DECICE framework aims to support flexible integration across Cloud-Edge environments, facilitating interoperability and dynamic adaptation. Users interact with the framework through standard Kubernetes interfaces, extended with DECICE-specific functionalities that simplify the deployment and management of complex, distributed workloads. This structured architecture, grounded in well-established open-source tools, positions DECICE to address the unique challenges of heterogeneous, multi-tiered systems, enabling a robust, modular, and efficient solution for Cloud-to-Edge computing needs.

Figure 17 depicts the cluster pilot that will be used for development and validation of the use cases.

Phase 1: Cluster pilot for development and validation

Figure 17: DECICE Cluster pilot used for development and validation of use cases.

The DECICE project’s technical stack for the initial development and validation phase integrates open-source and specialized tools to enable adaptive orchestration, real-time monitoring, and AI-driven workload management across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. The cluster pilot infrastructure consists of 28 ARM-based compute nodes, with additional nodes dedicated to AI model training and inference, and two high-throughput storage nodes to support data-intensive applications. Kubernetes serves as the core orchestrator for distributed workloads, extended by Kubeedge for seamless integration of Edge devices that operate autonomously in resource-constrained environments. Volcano further supports high-performance computing (HPC) and batch tasks, optimizing scheduling for computationally demanding workloads. Prometheus provides real-time system monitoring, collecting essential metrics that inform both the digital twin and AI scheduler for adaptive resource management. The stack includes SEDNA for collaborative AI workflows, enabling federated learning and inference across Cloud and Edge resources. The digital twin within DECICE leverages AI models to predict system behavior and optimize resource usage dynamically, facilitating real-time adjustments to workload placement and system configurations. Together, these technologies establish a robust and flexible framework that supports DECICE’s objectives for energy-efficient, intelligent orchestration across diverse, distributed computing environments.

7.3 Validating Use Cases

The DECICE framework is validated through a series of real-world use cases across diverse fields, each designed to demonstrate the framework’s capacity for responsive, efficient, and secure management of Cloud-Edge applications.

7.3.1 Intelligent Intersection with VRU Detection

In the context of connected and autonomous vehicles, intersections present heightened safety challenges due to the variety of road users and the need for rapid, precise detection to prevent accidents. This use case, focused on road safety, utilizes cameras positioned at intersections to detect vulnerable road users (VRUs) such as pedestrians and cyclists. DECICE enables low-latency processing and high detection accuracy, with the system achieving object recognition rates above 95% and processing times under one second. The framework

supports adaptive load balancing and resource allocation to meet the demands of this safety-critical application, ensuring responsive and efficient use of resources.

7.3.2 MRI Scans for Medical Imaging

MRI scans are crucial in medical diagnostics but present computational and data privacy challenges due to their high-resolution, sensitive data. This use case explores DECICE's ability to perform fast, secure analysis of MRI images, where Edge devices initially handle data but may offload intensive computations to Cloud resources if needed. The framework enforces stringent data privacy measures, ensuring that data is securely stored and only accessible by authorized devices.

7.3.3 In-the-Field Intelligence for Emergency Response

For emergency response scenarios, timely, flexible data processing is essential to support dynamic and hazardous environments. This use case integrates data from drones and satellites to provide real-time intelligence and operational support in the field. DECICE enables efficient processing of data on the Edge, allowing for rapid adaptation to environmental variables like area size, energy availability, and connectivity constraints. The system's ability to replan missions in under a minute and to detect people in real time (<10 seconds) demonstrates its capability to support critical, adaptive decision-making in emergency situations, maximizing responsiveness and resource efficiency.

7.4 More Information and How to Engage

To stay updated on the latest activities and developments within the DECICE project, visit our official Website at <https://www.decice.eu/>, where information on upcoming events, the project's objectives, and recent news can be found. Additional resources, including publications, datasets, and technical materials, are available through our Zenodo community page at <https://zenodo.org/communities/decice-project/>.

8 Discussion and Outlook

8.1 Comparison of Orchestration Approaches

The white paper presents the approaches of six EU projects with respect to the management of resources in the CEI continuum. The six projects share goals and methodologies in their efforts to advance the state of the art in Edge-Cloud resource management and optimization. **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrates the main characteristics of each project, including their overall approach, their main use cases, as well as their distinguishing features.

Table 1: Comparison of the Different Approaches to Edge Cloud Orchestration.

Project	Overview	Use Cases	Unique Features
CODECO	Cross-layer orchestration with Kubernetes integration	Smart cities, vehicular digital twins, Energy (smart grid integration, buildings), MDS, automated robots in manufacturing with decentralised management	Context-awareness (energy, resilience), integrated network-compute-data orchestration
COGNIFOG	Cognitive fog computing for CEI integration	Urban crisis management, e-health	Multi-cluster orchestration, energy-efficient placement
COGNIT	Serverless Edge-Cloud management	Traffic management, wildfire detection	Serverless functions, AI-driven optimization, energy efficiency
MLSysOps	AI-driven system management for Cloud-Edge-IoT	Smart agriculture, smart cities	Hierarchical AI architecture, explainable AI
ENACT	Cognitive computing continuum with zero-touch provisioning	Media streaming, digital twin platforms	Dynamic graph modelling, AI-enabled forecasting
DECICE	Decentralized approach reducing dependency on centralized infrastructures e.g., Kubernetes for orchestration	Intelligent Intersections, Infield intelligence for emergency response, Secure analysis of MRI images at the Edge	High scalability without a need to rely on centralized control points; AI-enabled workload adaptation

The analysed projects have the following similarities:

- **AI and Machine Learning Integration:** All projects utilize AI and machine learning to enhance resource management and optimize operations across the Edge-Cloud continuum. This includes workload prediction, resource allocation, and system automation.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Each one of the projects emphasizes scalable solutions that can adapt to dynamic workloads and environments. As a prominent example, several

projects use container orchestration technologies like Kubernetes to manage resources efficiently, while there are projects (e.g., DECICE) that achieve scalability based on a decentralized approach to managing resources.

- **Cross-Layer Resource Management:** The projects focus on managing resources across different layers of the network stack. In this way, they strive to ensure optimal distribution of tasks between Edge and Cloud environments.
- **Security and Privacy:** One of the common priorities of all projects is to ensure secure data flow and protecting sensitive information is a common priority. In this direction, projects implement robust encryption, authentication protocols, and privacy-preserving techniques.
- **Heterogeneous Environment Support:** All projects provide middleware systems that are designed to operate across diverse computing environments, from IoT devices to Cloud data centres. Hence, all projects address the challenges of managing heterogeneous resources.
- **Focus on Energy Efficiency:** The projects incorporate strategies for energy-efficient resource management. They consider the environmental impact and sustainability of their operations.

Considering the described characteristics, the approaches employed by the projects differ in several aspects. CODECO focuses on cross-layer orchestration with Kubernetes for flexible deployment, while COGNIFOG emphasizes cognitive fog computing to enable seamless CEI integration. COGNIT uses a serverless approach to manage resources efficiently across the continuum. MLSysOps implements an AI-driven framework for managing heterogeneous resources. Finally, ENACT leverages cognitive computing and zero-touch provisioning for dynamic resource management, while DECICE leverages AI-driven techniques for real-time adaptation of workloads across Edge and Cloud environments, towards ensuring that resources are optimally allocated based on dynamic conditions. Moreover, each project comes with its unique features and value propositions.

The key differentiators are as follows:

- **CODECO:** Focuses on automating the deployment of containerized applications and their micro-services, employing context-awareness and AI/ML, as well as focusing on the application QoS requirements (including energy and security). Orchestrates the infrastructure in an integrated way across three layers of resources: network, computational and data observability.
- **COGNIFOG:** Emphasizes energy-efficient resource placement and integration in CEI environments using cognitive fog computing principles, tailored for critical urban and healthcare applications.
- **COGNIT:** Leverages serverless computing to streamline resource management and optimization, particularly for energy-efficient, dynamic environments such as traffic management and disaster response.
- **MLSysOps:** Adopts hierarchical and explainable AI architectures, making it suitable for complex IoT systems like smart agriculture and urban planning. Its focus on transparency enhances trust and usability.
- **ENACT:** Relies on cognitive computing and zero-touch provisioning, utilizing dynamic graph modeling and forecasting to optimize resource allocation for real-time applications like media streaming and digital twins.
- **DECICE:** Excels in decentralization, reducing reliance on centralized orchestration systems such as Kubernetes. It emphasizes scalability and rapid adaptation through AI-enabled workload distribution in critical Edge scenarios.

In conclusion, each approach targets specific challenges in Edge-Cloud resource management, offering unique strengths aligned with their focus areas. CODECO and COGNIFOG stand out for their integration and energy efficiency strategies, while COGNIT and DECICE emphasize flexibility and decentralization. MLSysOps and ENACT excel in leveraging AI and cognitive computing for predictive, scalable solutions in dynamic and heterogeneous environments.

8.2 Best Practices

Based on the work and outcomes of the presented projects, we herewith present a range of best practices illustrated in Figure 18 that can be applied towards effective resource management across the Edge-Cloud continuum:

- **Best Practice #1 - AI-Driven Optimization:** Use machine learning and other forms of AI to predict workloads, optimize resource allocation, and automate scaling processes. The use of AI enhances efficiency and reduces operational costs due to the ability of AI systems to dynamically adapt to changing demands.
- **Best Practice #2 - Cross-Layer integrated Orchestration:** It is recommended to implement cross-layer orchestration to manage resources seamlessly across the Cloud-Edge continuum. This involves coordinating data flows, computation, and networking services to ensure optimal resource distribution.
- **Best Practice #3 - Scalability and Flexibility:** Design systems that are scalable and flexible to handle varying workloads efficiently. Use container orchestration technologies like Kubernetes to manage resources across multiple clusters.
- **Best Practice #4 - Security and Privacy:** Prioritize security based on robust encryption and authentication protocols. It is also advised to implement privacy-preserving techniques to protect sensitive data across distributed environments.
- **Best Practice #5 - Energy Efficiency:** Focus on energy-efficient resource management strategies to minimize environmental impact. This includes optimizing data placement and using energy-efficient algorithms.
- **Best Practice #6 - Heterogeneous Environment Support:** Ensure support for heterogeneous environments based on well-designed solutions that can operate across diverse computing platforms, from IoT devices to Cloud data centers.
- **Best Practice #6 - Function-as-a-Service (FaaS):** Leverage serverless architectures like FaaS for applications requiring high scalability and low latency. This approach allows for efficient handling of isolated, stateless functions triggered by specific events.
- **Best Practice #7 - Real-Time Monitoring and Telemetry:** Implement real-time monitoring tools to track system performance, detect anomalies, and provide insights into infrastructure health. This is a key to maintaining reliability and efficiency.
- **Best Practice #8 - Dynamic Scheduling and Workload Migration:** Use dynamic scheduling techniques to match applications with available infrastructure optimally. This involves factoring computational, network, and data properties towards effective workload migration.
- **Best Practice #9 - Interoperability and Modularity:** Design systems with modular architectures that allow components to be updated or replaced without disrupting the entire system. It is important to ensure interoperability across different layers of the Cloud-Edge continuum.

Figure 18: Best Practices for Effective Resources Management.

These best practices can be combined in the scope of middleware platforms for the management and optimization of resources in Edge-Cloud environments. This combination can ensure efficient, secure, and scalable operations across diverse applications and use cases.